
Subject Gateway: A Useful Tool For Enhancing Library Services

Dr. Pravin A.Joshi

Librarian, M.E.S.Arts & Commerce College Mehkar

Corresponding Author - Dr. Pravin A.Joshi

DOI -10.5281/zenodo.15560003

Abstract:

Since in this age of Internet and AI there is rapid growth of digital information. But in this huge digital information production relevant information is scattered and very hard to find required information and get access for it. To overcome this problem subject gateway may be the very useful tools for providing specific required information to end user in minimum times. Subject gateways allow libraries to explore the usefulness of their subject expertise in this digital age. The summary of this research paper focuses on significance of subject gateway as tools to enhance library services. It also highlights on their features and their impact on information access and management.

Keyword: Subject Gateways, Library Services, Information Discovery, User Experience, Digital Libraries

Introduction:

As information technology makes many advances in the field of library and information science, it also have problem of ‘too much information’ available on digital platform. In this era of information overload it presents both challenges and opportunities’ for libraries. An internet contain huge amount of scholarly information and made it easier, faster to analyze collect, search and information. But the information may be scattered not only in several different format but also on completely different systems, some of which users may not be able to access. Since the internet offers a vast sea of information, navigating it effectively can be difficult for users. To overcome this problem the concept of ‘Subject Gateways’ emerged. Subject Gateways address this challenge by acting as specialized search engines and guides,

providing focused access to relevant and reliable within a particular subject domain.

Objectives:

The primary objective of the research is to explore, analyze and demonstrate how subject gateways can serve as effective tools in improving the accessibility.

Understanding the Subject Gateway:

- Assesing User Needs.
- Evaluating Benefits.
- Exploring Implementation.
- Promoting User Engagement.
- Improving Library Services.
- Identifying Challenges.

Subject Gateways:

Subject gateways are web-based platforms that offer access to a wide range of

online resources related to a specific subject. It is an internet based service. It provides access to electronics resources. Subject gateways include searchable databases which allow users to search across multiple resources simultaneously. It also provide subject guide to provide organized lists of relevant websites, article and other resources. Subject gateways provides links to library resources to integrate with the library's own collections such as e-databases. It also provides expert-curated content and user friendly interface which make it easy for users to navigate and find the information they need.

Generally resources are catalogued in a database, using some standards such as MARC and different cataloguing rules for electronics documents. There is field available in the record that contain a hyperlink to the full text on the internet. Resources are not harvested but selected using strict quality criteria like originality and others. The subject gateways not only points to the sources, it recommends them which is the main difference between a gateway and an internet searching machine.

Definition:

“ A process of identification, filtering, description, classification and infexing before they are added to databases which is freely available via a www.”
..... **Maffat.**

“Subject gateway are internet based services designed to help users locate high quality information that is available on the Internet.
.....**Emma Place. ILRT, University of Bristol.**

So we can say that gateways are the internet search tools to help prole to find

resources on the internet such as e-books,e-journals, e-databases, articals, papers,reports, bibliographical databases and many more. Subject gateways is nothing but the facility that allows easier access to networked-based resources in a particular subject area. In other words subject gateways are the set of webpages containing lists of link to resources. It have emerged as powerful tools for improving user experience and promoting effectives information discovery. Hence subject gateways help to transform library service in the digital age.

Characteristics:

- Subject gateways selective, pointing only to internet resources that meet with selection criteria.
- They are limited to specific subject.
- Subject gateways policy declaring what subjects they are indexing.
- They are built by subject and information specialists.
- It has rich resources description containing relevant information.
- It has distributed cataloguing that is scattered group of subject specialists contributed databases.

Benefits of Subject Gateways for Libraries:

- Enhanced User Experience:
- Improved information discovery: Subject gateways help users find relevant information quickly and efficiently.
- Improved user satisfaction: By providing a curated and organized experience, subject gateways can

enhance user satisfaction with library services.

- Reduced information overload: Subject gateways help users navigate the vast amount of information available online, reducing the risk of information overload.
- Improved Library Services:
- Enhanced information literacy: Subject gateways can help users develop critical information literacy skills by teaching them how to evaluate and use online resources effectively.
- Increased visibility of library resources: By integrating with library collections, subject gateways can increase the visibility and use of library resources.
- Improved library image: Subject gateways can showcase the library as a valuable resource for information and research.
- Cost-effectiveness:
- Reduced duplication of effort: Subject gateways can help libraries avoid duplicating efforts in creating and maintaining subject-specific resources.
- Increased efficiency: By streamlining the information discovery process, subject gateways can increase the efficiency of library services.

Content on Subject Gateways:

For Creation of subject gateways, we can use the following information in specific subject and create an effective subject gateway:

- E- books,

- E- Journals.
- Thesis and Dissertations databases (ETDs).
- Bibliographies.
- Conference proceeding.
- Encyclopedias and Dictionaries.
- Weblogs and listservs.
- Fellowships and Grants.
- Research Centers and Laboratories.
- Professional Association and Societies.
- Patent and IPR...and etc.

Criteria for quality assessment of Subject Gateways:

Following criteria can decide quality of subject gateways.

- Authority and reputation of the source-Who provided the information.
- Accuracy-is the Information is accurate.
- Validity- Do the resource fulfills the stated purpose.
- Comprehensiveness- to what level of details does the resource go.
- Uniqueness- Is the information on the site unique.
- Composition- Is the Information well composed.
- Ease of Navigation- Is it to navigate the resource.
- Use of recognized standards.
- Appropriate Format.
- Provision of user support.
- Up to date Information.
- Technical performance of the resource acceptable.

Free websites for creation of subject gateways:

- **Google Sites:**

A User-friendly platform to create websites with customizable templates. We can organize subject specific links, resources and documents. This facility is free to use with google account.

- **WordPress.com:**

A free platform for creating blogs or websites. It is suitable for creating a subject gateway with posts or pages categorized by subject.

- **WEEBLY:**

Easy to use platform for creating a free websites or portal. It provides options for categorizing and linking resources effectively.

- **Padlet:**

A Collaborative tool that allow you to create a visual board for resource sharing. We can create public page for our subject gateway and share the link.

- **Notion:**

A powerful tool for organizing and sharing resources in a structured way. We can create public page for our subject gateway and share the link. It is free with google account.

Popular Subject gateways available on web:

- AGRIGATE (Agriculture, Forestry, Environment, Food Science, Horticulture).
- BIOGATE (Biological science).
- BIOME (Health and Life Science).
- CHEMDEX (Chemistry).

- OMNI (Biomedical Sciences).
- EEVL (Engineering).
- PSIGATE (Physical Science).
- ADAM (Art, Design, Architecture and Media).
- AHDS (Arts and Humanities).
- RDN (Reference Source).
- SOSIG (Social Sciences).
- EDNA ONLINE (Educational Network).

Google Scholar: A popular academic search engine that provides access to scholarly literature across many disciplines.

PubMed: A biomedical literature database that provides access to millions of citations from biomedical literature.

JSTOR: A digital library that provides access to academic journals, books, and primary sources.

Conclusion:

Subject gateways are valuable tools for enhancing library services in the digital age. Subject gateways provide opportunities to librarians for update their subject. By providing curated access to high-quality resources, subject gateways can improve user experience, enhance information literacy, and increase the visibility of library collections. The subject gateways may be extended to individual departments of an organization which allow the users of specific group to access their specific resources. As the volume of digital information continues to grow, subject gateways will play an increasingly important role in helping libraries fulfill their mission of providing access to information and supporting research and learning.

Further Research:

1. Explore the impact of subject gateways on user information-seeking behavior.
2. Investigate the challenges and best practices for developing and maintaining subject gateways.
3. Analyze the role of subject gateways in supporting interdisciplinary research.

References:

1. Dempsey, lorcan (2000).“The subject gateway: experiences and issues based on the emergence of the Resource Discovery Network”.

- Online Information review, vol.24 (1).pp 8-23.
2. M Pandu,(2012), “Subject gateways to health science information: An Evaluation study, Vol I iss No 3 pp 181-19-.
 3. Jerry v. Caswell(2006), Leveraging resources in a library gateway”, Library Hi Tech,Vol 24 iss No I pp. 142-152.
 4. URL <https://www.ala.org/acrl> ;- Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL):
 5. URL: <https://pps.goosle.com/products/sites>